

DESIGN OF FIBRE-POLYMER COMPOSITE STRUCTURES (CEN/TS 19101): OVERVIEW, COMMENTARY AND WORKED EXAMPLES

Luigi Ascione, University of Salerno, Italy, l.ascione@unisa.it
João R. Correia, CERIS, IST, University of Lisbon, Portugal, joao.ramoa.correia@tecnico.ulisboa.pt
Thomas Keller, CCLAB, EPFL, Switzerland, thomas.keller@epfl.ch
Jan Knippers, University of Stuttgart, Germany, jan.knippers@itke.uni-stuttgart.de
Toby Mottram, University of Warwick, UK, Toby.Mottram@warwick.ac.uk
Carlo Paulotto, Ferrovial, Spain, cpaulotto@ferrovial.com
José Sena-Cruz, ISISE, University of Minho, Portugal, jsena@civil.uminho.pt

ABSTRACT

During the current revision of the first generation of Eurocodes, which started in 2016 and will end in 2025, the European Community decided to start to develop a Eurocode for fibre-polymer composite structures. According to the CEN procedure, an Eurocode has to be preceded by a Technical Specification (TS) and, after a period of trial use, the TS can then be converted into a Eurocode. This paper gives an overview of the European TS CEN/TS 19101: 2022, published in November 2022, and of two of its complementary documents, respectively a commentary, of about 1000 pages, and a collection of fifteen worked examples.

KEYWORDS

Materials; Design; Structural Analysis; CEN Technical Specification; Eurocodes.

INTRODUCTION

In 2012, the European Commission issued the Mandate M/515 for a detailed work programme to amend the existing Eurocodes and extend the scope of structural Eurocodes. The work of the CEN/Technical Committee (TC) 250 “Structural Eurocodes” (CEN/TC 250, 2020) under the Mandate M/515 started in 2016 and the second generation of the Eurocodes is expected to be published by 2026. During the current revision of the first generation of Eurocodes, it was decided to start to develop a Eurocode for fibre-polymer composite structures, following the classic procedure envisaged by CEN and consisting of three successive phases (CEN/TC 250, 2020).

In consideration of this, the Working Group WG 4 of CEN/TC 250 was appointed, under the convenorship of Luigi Ascione. The first generation of Eurocodes did not include a Eurocode for fibre-polymer composite structures (referred to as composite structures in the following, also known as Fibre-Reinforced Polymer (FRP) structures).

In a first phase, a Scientific and Technical Research Report (Ascione et al., 2016) was published, aimed at promoting the debate in Europe on the subject of the design of composite structures. Based on this report, the development of a CEN Technical Specification (TS) ‘*Design of Fibre-Polymer Composite Structures*’ was initiated and a Project Team WG4.T2 (PT), associated with WG 4, was nominated in July 2018 to prepare this document, under the leadership of João Ramôa Correia. The other members of the PT were Thomas Keller, Jan Knippers, Toby Mottram, Carlo Paulotto, José Sena-Cruz (since 09/2020) and Till Vallée (until 11/2019). The TS represents the second step of the general procedure established by CEN/TC 250 towards a new Eurocode, which is expected to be completed by 2026. The conversion of the TS by CEN/TC 250, after a period for trial use and commenting, into a new Eurocode will be the third and last step.

The information provided in this paper corresponds to the most up-to-date state of the procedure, which has undergone a significant acceleration in the last year and a half due to the publication of the TS (with

introduction of important changes or additions to the text compared to previous drafts), as well as the finalization of the two complementary documents (Keller et al., 2020) and (Ascione et al., 2022): the Commentary and the Worked Examples.

The denomination change from FRP to Fibre-Polymer Composite Structures was motivated by the fact that the former does not adequately reflect the structural roles of the two components (fibres and polymer) in the composite material. Furthermore, the new denomination is in line with that in other European languages, which all include the term ‘composite’ or ‘composites’ in an equivalent translation. It would be desirable that no acronyms (such as FRP, GFRP, CFRP) are used anymore to give a clear identity to our materials.

Three subsequent drafts of the TS have been subjected to revision by the European National Standardization Bodies (NSBs), of which the last was followed by an internal ballot between the members of CEN TC 250 on the conversion of FprCEN / TS 19101 to EN status, with the possibility of comments by voters. The final text of the TS, as revised after the internal ballot, was submitted in April 2022 to Formal Vote by the National Members of CEN, who approved it in July 2022. The text approved includes twelve clauses and five annexes (Table 1).

Table 1: Table of contents of the TS

1. Scope
2. Normative references
3. Terms, definition and symbols
4. Basis of design
5. Materials
6. Durability
7. Structural analysis
8. Ultimate limit states
9. Serviceability limit states
10. Fatigue
11. Detailing
12. Connections and joints
Annex A (informative) Creep coefficients
Annex B (informative) Indicative values of material properties for preliminary design
Annex C (informative) Buckling of orthotropic laminates and profiles
Annex D (normative) Structural fire design
Annex E (informative) Bridge details

In November 2022, the TS has been announced and made available to producers, designers and contractors at a national level, even if conflicting national standards may continue to exist. The German and French translations are also available.

The main features of the TS, as well as of the Commentary and Worked Examples, will be summarized in the following sections.

SCOPE OF THE TS

The scope of the TS is pointed out in clause 1. The TS applies to the design of buildings, bridges, and other civil engineering structures, including permanent and temporary structures, made with composite materials or combinations of composite and other structural materials (for hybrid-composite structures).

The structural members addressed by the document are made of (Figure 1) composite laminates, profiles and sandwich panels (including web-core panels), with bolted and bonded joints, made of glass, carbon, basalt or aramid fibres, thermoset resins and adhesives, and polymeric foam or balsa wood cores. More

explicitly, composite cables, concrete rebar, strengthening components and honeycomb cores are not covered by the TS.

Figure 1: Structural components addressed by the TS

The main manufacturing processes covered by the document are pultrusion, filament winding, hand layup, resin transfer moulding (RTM), resin infusion moulding (RIM), and vacuum-assisted resin transfer moulding (VARTM).

The TS applies to composite structures in which the material temperatures in the members, joints and components, under service conditions, are higher than -40°C and lower than $T_g - 20^{\circ}\text{C}$, where T_g is the lowest glass transition temperature of either the composite, the core or adhesive materials. T_g is specified as the onset value of the storage modulus decay, obtained from dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA), according to the procedure indicated in the standard ISO 6271-11 (Figure 2). It should be at least 60°C .

1: Glassy state; 2: Inflection point in glass transition region; 3: Tangent lines

Figure 2: Determination of T_g

TERMS, DEFINITIONS AND SYMBOLS

The terms are introduced in clause 3 relating to the constituent materials, manufacturing, composite components and members, design, failure modes, joints and connections, and defects. In the same clause, a detailed list of symbols and abbreviations is included, and conventions and member axes are specified.

BASIS OF DESIGN

The basis of design is presented in clause 4 in accordance to the general rules given in (CEN/TC 250, 2018), supplemented by provisions that are specific to composite structures. According to the rules for the limit state design, the design value of resistance, R_d , for a specific design situation should be determined from:

$$R_d = \frac{1}{\gamma_{Rd} \cdot \gamma_m} R \{ \eta_{c,i} \cdot X_{k,i}; a_d \} \quad (1)$$

where

- γ_{Rd} is a partial factor taking into account the uncertainty in the resistance model, and geometrical deviations, if these are not modelled explicitly.
- γ_m is a partial factor taking into account the unfavourable deviations of the representative material or product properties from their characteristic values, and geometrical deviations.
- $R\{\dots\}$ denotes the output of the resistance model.
- $\eta_{c,i}$ is the total conversion factor, taking into account effects of moisture and temperature, effects of ageing of materials, including the uncertainty of those effects.
- $X_{k,i}$ represents the characteristic values of the material or product properties.
- a_d denotes the design values of the geometrical parameters.
- i takes into account the i^{th} material.

For the design of creep rupture, fatigue, adhesive connections, and fire, the product $\gamma_{Rd} \cdot \gamma_m$ is replaced by γ_M , which is a single partial material factor considering all the uncertainties and deviations mentioned above.

Partial factors

The partial factor for a material or product property, γ_m , depends only on its coefficient of variation and shall be determined by testing.

For the partial factor for the resistance model, γ_{Rd} , the values are provided in the TS for (i) profiles and laminates (for material failure, and global and local buckling); (ii) sandwich panels (for material failure, global and local buckling, laminate wrinkling, core indentation and punching failure); and (iii) bolted joints (for net-tension, pin-bearing, shear-out, block shear, and pull-out failure). Where possible, the values of γ_{Rd} provided in the TS were derived from detailed statistical analyses of a significant number of resistance models, based on the assumptions of (CEN/TC 250, 2018) and (CEN ISO, 2015); some of the values were also validated or calibrated through explicit reliability analyses.

Conversion factors

The total conversion factor, η_c , is presented in the TS as the product of two conversion factors for temperature, η_{ct} , and moisture effects, η_{cm} , so: $\eta_c = \eta_{ct} \cdot \eta_{cm}$. The nominal values are provided for specific composites, core and adhesive materials, as well as for specific environmental conditions, for a 50-year period (which may be extended, if appropriate maintenance and inspection procedures are implemented). The nominal values provided in the TS were derived from the experimental results collected from the literature. As an alternative to the nominal conversion factors, the temperature- and

moisture-dependent material properties may be determined by testing in accordance to Annex D of (CEN/TC 250, 2018). The same applies for any properties affected by environmental conditions not covered by the nominal conversion factors provided.

The conversion factor for temperature, η_{ct} , takes into account the changes of material properties due to the material temperatures under service conditions relative to the material temperatures at 20°C, excluding any effects of long-term exposure. Nominal values are provided for the composite materials; in composite materials, these depend on whether the properties are fibre- or matrix-dominated and are function of T_g (and the service temperature). Further values are provided for polymeric foams and balsa wood sandwich core materials, with the former also depending on T_g and the latter on density.

The conversion factor for moisture, η_{cm} , takes into account any changes of the material properties due to moisture absorption over time, including ageing effects resulting from long-term exposure. The nominal values of η_{cm} were derived for unprotected composite materials and epoxy adhesives, for three exposure classes: class I represents indoor exposure; class II basically concerns outdoor exposure without continuous exposure to water or high relative humidity; while class III basically represents continuous exposure to water or high relative humidity. Also in this case, the nominal values provided were derived from experimental values collected from the literature.

Creep effects

A sub-clause concerning creep effects is further included, complemented by Annex A. Effects of creep on both strength and deformations are taken into account. The creep effects on strength are addressed by limiting the stress levels in composite members and components for the quasi-permanent combinations of actions. The creep effects on deformations are taken into account by creep coefficients, which reduce the relevant elastic moduli of the materials. The values of the creep coefficients are specified for different moduli for pultruded composite profiles, composite laminates/plies, and core materials, for a 50-year period; they were derived from experimental results collected from the literature. Annex A provides further values for additional periods of design service life.

MATERIALS

This topic is addressed in clause 5. In this clause, standard test methods are listed to obtain the composite, core and adhesive material properties normally required in the design of composite structures. Preferably, the TS refers to EN ISO standards; alternatively, reference to ASTM standards is made.

Instructions on how to extract or manufacture test coupons are also provided, to avoid damaging a composite member and also when the laminates are relatively thick.

For a preliminary design, the indicative (mean) values of selected material properties are listed in Annex B, which can be applied, provided that appropriate values of the coefficients of variation are assumed to derive the characteristic (design) values.

DURABILITY

Clause 6 provides guidance regarding the selection and processing of constituent materials. The most relevant environmental conditions and their main effects on material properties over time are described. Recommendations are also provided on whether protective measures should be applied, for both composite members and their connections and joints. The clause considers the environmental conditions of temperature, moisture (humidity, water), chemicals, and ultraviolet (UV) radiation, acting in isolation or in combination.

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

Detailed provisions for the structural analysis of composite laminates, profiles, sandwich panels, joints and hybrid composite structures are provided in clause 7.

Sandwich panels, composed of thin face sheets and homogeneous cores (flexible or rigid) or web cores, are explicitly taken into account.

Joints - simple, semi-continuous and continuous - are also addressed in this clause.

Provisions on the first-order analysis, based on the initial geometry of the structure, and second-order analysis, taking into account the influence of the deformation of the structure, with consideration of any imperfections, are given.

Analytical and finite element modelling approaches for composite laminates, profiles and sandwich panels are subsequently provided.

ULTIMATE LIMIT STATES

Ultimate limit state (ULS) verifications for composite laminates, profiles and sandwich panels are described in four sub-clauses of clause 8 and one Annex (Annex C for laminates and profiles). The ULS verification for creep rupture is also provided.

Regarding the laminates, ULS verification formulae are provided for balanced symmetrical laminates in the cases of in-plane axial, shear and bending stresses, out-of-plane tensile and bending stresses, interlaminar shear stresses, and combined stresses.

Whereas for profiles, the TS provides some ULS verification formulae in terms of internal forces and moments for the most common states of stress, i.e. axial forces, bending, shear, transverse compression, torsion, and combinations of axial forces and bending, and bending and shear.

Table 2 summarizes the ULS verifications for sandwich panels: 20 verifications are required. This last topic has been subject to major revision with respect to (Ascione et al., 2016).

Table 2: Failure modes in homogenous-core and web-core sandwich panels

Sandwich component	Failure mode	Homogeneous-core		Web-core	
		Rigid core	Flexible core	With core infill	Without core infill
Face sheet	Face sheet tensile failure	x	x	x	x
	Face sheet crushing	x	x	x	x
	Face sheet wrinkling	x	x	x	
	Face sheet local buckling				x
Core	Core shear failure	x	x	x	
	Core in-plane tensile or compressive failure	x		x	
	Core out-of-plane tensile or compressive failure	x	x	x	
	Core indentation	x	x	x	
	Core punching failure	x			
Web	Web shear failure			x	x
	Web wrinkling due to shear			x	
	Web local buckling due to shear				x
	Web bending failure			x	x
	Web wrinkling due to in-plane bending			x	
	Web local buckling due to in-plane bending				x
	Web crushing due to transverse compression			x	x
	Web wrinkling due to transverse compression			x	
Web local buckling due to transverse compression				x	
Interface	Face sheet/core delamination	x	x	x	
Sandwich	Global buckling	x	x	x	x

In addition to the typical laminate failure modes and core shear failure, the sub-clause includes face sheet wrinkling, core indentation and core punching failures. Regarding the face sheet-core interface, interface failure must not occur; failure must occur in the core, which requires testing for verification.

SERVICEABILITY LIMIT STATES

This topic is addressed in clause 9. The serviceability criteria considered include deflections, vibrations, and matrix cracking of composite laminates. The latter should be prevented by considering the limits of the tensile strain due to the frequent combination of actions, considering the effects of creep in permanent and quasi-permanent loads. Values are provided for tensile strain causing matrix cracking of composite laminates made of polyester and epoxy resins.

FATIGUE

This topic is addressed in clause 10. The approach followed in the TS requires carrying out the fatigue verification, at the structural member or joint levels, in terms of stress resultants, *i.e.* internal forces and/or moments. This is because fatigue failure normally occurs at locations where geometrical changes in sections or changes in materials generate stress concentrations, thus a stress-based verification could be difficult. Furthermore, testing at the member and joint levels inherently takes into account any geometrical and material imperfections and size effects.

The fatigue action model for traffic loads should be derived from the project specification and (CEN/TC 250, 1991), taking into account the mean stress level, to which the fatigue life of composite structures is sensitive. A difficulty in this respect is that the Fatigue Load Models (FLMs) of (CEN/TC 1991), FML1-FML3, are not tailored to composite bridges and are therefore not applicable. Furthermore, FLM4 represents a Variable Amplitude (VA) loading. Applying a VA fatigue verification may cause two significant problems for the design of composite structures, *i.e.*: (i) the testing effort may be considerable, and (ii) the Miner's linear damage rule (on which the method is based) may significantly over- or under-estimate the fatigue life. This method is therefore not considered applicable to the fatigue verification of composite structures.

The fatigue verification is performed in two successive steps:

Step 1: First of all, it has to be checked whether this verification is needed or not on the basis of a well-known criterion provided by the TS.

Step 2: Application of Eq. 1, in which: (i) a single partial material factor for the fatigue resistance, γ_{MF} has to be utilized, as mentioned above; (ii) the characteristic value of the fatigue resistance of a member or joint is obtained from member or joint testing, at constant amplitude cycles; (iii) the conversion factors for static loading are assumed to also be applicable to fatigue.

The values of the partial factor γ_{MF} provided by the TS depend on (i) the type of inspection and maintenance and accessibility of the critical details, and (ii) the consequences of failure, *i.e.* whether or not a member or joint is fail-safe, in accordance to (Clarke, 1996) and the content of the sub-clause 8.3.4.4(1) of (CEN/TC 250, 2018).

Qualification and proof testing are specified; the former refers to D4(1a) and the latter to D4(1e) of (CEN/TC 250, 2018), respectively. For bridges, the required number of fatigue tests and fatigue cycles in qualification testing is indicated according to the traffic category, for a 100-year design service life. Proof testing shall be defined case by case in the project-specific quality plan.

DETAILING

Provisions concerning detailing are given in clause 11 in order to minimize any stress concentrations, detrimental effects of environmental conditions, and effects of tolerances and imperfections. The provisions address profiles, sandwich panels and member laminates, as well as bolted and adhesive connections.

Annex E, of an informative type, shows typical details for bridges, such as bearings, expansion joints, parapets, and crash barrier fixations.

CONNECTIONS AND JOINTS

Clause 12 is devoted to the connections, subdivided into three sub-clauses, for bolted, adhesive and hybrid bolted-adhesive connections, and joints (whereby a joint is composed of one or more individual connections).

Regarding bolted connections under in-plane forces, the resistances in the case of laminate failure modes to be verified are net-tension, pin-bearing (Figure 3), shear-out, and block-shear failure.

Figure 3: Pin-bearing failure mode for a single bolt under in-plane forces

Subjected to out-of-plane tensile forces, the failure modes at the bolt locations are pull-out failure through the laminate, bolt failure in tension, and failure of the laminate at a bolt location owing to interaction between in- and out-of-plane forces (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Typical failure modes of bolted connections subject to out-of-plane tensile forces

At the joint level, shear and tying force failures of web cleat joints are considered (Figure 5).

1: Beam web; 2: Composite web cleat; 3: delamination failure location.
Figure 5: Tying force failure for a pair of composite web cleats

A composite structure comprising adhesive joints shall be designed as fail-safe, i.e. joint failure shall not result in failure of the structure or critical parts thereof. Failure of an adhesive joint is considered as an accidental situation according to (CEN/TC 250, 2018). The failure mode of adhesive connections shall be either cohesive failure in the adhesive or fibre-tear failure in the adherend; adhesive failure, i.e. failure in the adherend-adhesive interface, shall be prevented by appropriate material selection and surface preparation (Figure 6).

1: Adherend; 2: Adhesive layer; 3: Fibre-tear failure (inside composite adherent); 4: Cohesive failure (inside adhesive layer); 5: Adhesive failure (in adherent-adhesive layer surface)

Figure 6: Failure modes of adhesive connections

The resistance verification of adhesive connections is performed according to Eq. (1), using a single partial material factor for the adhesive connection resistance, $\gamma_{M,ac}$, as mentioned above. This partial factor depends on (i) the type of inspection and maintenance as well as the accessibility of the adhesive connection, and (ii) the application conditions, which can be either fully controlled, i.e. with reproducible process parameters, or only partially controlled parameters. Owing to insufficient experimental results, the range of values specified is adopted from sub-clause 5.1.10, P(4) of (Clarke, 1996), i.e. from the products of the partial factors $\gamma_{m,1} \cdot \gamma_{m,2}$. The background to these values could not be traced and therefore they require further validation. Three methods are described for the design of adhesive joints and connections: (i) design assisted by testing; (ii) design based on stress analysis; (iii) design based on fracture mechanics. Stress-based and fracture mechanics-based failure criteria are provided for the last two methods and experimental validation is mandatory in both cases.

Provisions are included for the design of hybrid bolted-adhesive connections. Depending on the relative stiffness of the adhesive layer, the individual resistances of the bolted and adhesive connections can be summed or not.

STRUCTURAL FIRE DESIGN

Annex D of the document applies to the design of composite structures for the accidental design situation of fire exposure. Composite structures that fulfil a load-bearing function, separating function or both are considered. The structure of this Annex complies with the parts concerning fire of the Eurocodes for other structural materials.

The first sub-clause provides the basis of design, including nominal and physically based fire exposures, actions, design values of material properties, verification methods, member analysis, analysis of parts of structures, global structural analysis, and fire protection measures.

The second sub-clause includes the material properties, i.e. thermal properties (emissivity coefficient, thermal conductivity, specific heat, density), and mechanical properties (strength and stiffness, thermal expansion coefficient). For each property, indicative, temperature-dependent values are given for the selected composite, foam and balsa core materials, wherever sufficient experimental data was available.

Further sub-clauses refer to tabulated design data and simplified design methods (for which no specific guidance is provided), and advanced design methods.

COMMENTARY AND WORKED EXAMPLES

The members of the PT drew up a collection of Background Documents and a collection of Worked Examples, both related to CEN/TS 19101. The latter were drafted with the collaboration of some members of WG 4.

The first collection consists of 395 individual Background Reports, which refer to individual relevant paragraphs. Twenty-nine authors and thirty-four reviewers were involved in drafting the Background Report. The authors and reviewers of each report are indicated at the beginning of it. Each report has been reviewed by at least two members of WG 4 or external experts.

The second collection consists of 15 step-by-step Worked Examples (WEs) for typical design cases in which the provisions of the TS are applied. It is the result of a joint activity between the members of the Project Team and members of WG 4. Two types of worked examples have been developed:

- Type A: Eleven schematic examples on the application of a specific provision of the TS.
- Type B: Four more elaborate examples on the design of structures or parts of structures.

All the WEs have been subjected to the review of at least two reviewers, experts in the field of the design of fibre-polymer composite structures. The authors and reviewers are indicated at the beginning of each WE. Tables 3 and 4 provide the list of WEs Type A and Type B, respectively.

It is the intention of the authors to publish the two complementary documents in two different books, whose editors are some of the authors of the present paper.

Table 3: WEs of Type A

No.	TITLE	AUTHOR(S)	REVIEWER(S)
A1	ULS verifications of a balanced symmetrical laminate subjected to in-plane and out-plane loading	José Sena-Cruz	João Ramoa Correia Luigi Ascione
A2	ULS verifications of a balanced symmetrical laminate subjected to in-plane and out-plane loading (preliminary design)	Wouter De Corte	João Ramoa Correia Luigi Ascione
A3	ULS verifications of a simply supported fibre-polymer composite profile with double symmetric H-cross-section subjected to axial compression	Mário Sá João Ramoa Correia	Luigi Ascione José Gonilha
A4	ULS and SLS verifications of a simply supported fibre-polymer composite profile with double symmetric I-cross-section subjected to a uniformly distributed transverse load	Mário Sá João Ramoa Correia	Luigi Ascione José Gonilha
A5	Verification of a loaded simply supported composite sandwich beam with complex balsa core	Wendel Sebastian Matthew Poulton Andre Pitt	Thomas Keller Marko Pavlovic
A6	ULS and SLS verifications of a simply supported fibre-polymer composite homogeneous-core sandwich panel subjected to a uniformly distributed transverse load	Mário Garrido João Ramoa Correia	Thomas Keller Marko Pavlovic
A7	ULS and SLS verifications of a simply supported fibre-polymer composite web-core sandwich panel subjected to a uniformly distributed transverse load	Mário Garrido João Ramoa Correia	Thomas Keller Marko Pavlovic
A8	ULS verification of double-lap adhesive joint with pultruded adherends (stress-based approach)	M. Pavlovic A. Christoforidou	Thomas Keller Luigi Ascione
A9	ULS verification of an adhesive double-lap joint with pultruded adherends (fracture-mechanics approach)	M. Pavlovic A. Christoforidou	Thomas Keller Luigi Ascione
A10	Buckling analysis and ULS verifications of 'H' and 'I' shape elements subjected to compression	Salvatore Russo	Nuno Silvestre Luigi Ascione
A11	ULS & SLS verifications of a simply supported fibre-polymer composite profile with double symmetric rectangular hollow (RHS) cross-section subjected to a uniformly distributed transverse load	João Ramoa Correia Mário Sá	Luigi Ascione José Gonilha

Table 4: WEs of Type B

No.	TITLE	AUTHOR(S)	REVIEWER(S)
B1	Ultimate Limit State (ULS) verifications for bolted connections of pultruded profiles of a truss bridge with a span length of 13.50 m	Matthias Oppe Reza Haghani Dogaheh	Toby Mottram Jan Knippers
B2	ULS verifications of a glass fibre reinforced polymer composite footbridge	E. Leprêtre S. Durand K. Brunellière J-F. Caron P. Jandin A. Pruvost	Carlo Paulotto Wendel Sebastian
B3	Design of a vacuum infused composite web-core sandwich traffic deck.	Remco Renting Jan Hiddingh Wouter Claassen Georgios Zarifis Lieuwe Cornelissen Liesbeth Tromp Ward Steijn Arjen Steenbrink Ane de Boer Johan de Boon Martijn Veltkamp	Thomas Keller Wendel Sebastian
B4	ULS analysis of spatial reticular Fibre-Polymer Composite structure	Salvatore Russo	Toby Mottram Matthias Oppe

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Regarding the document published in the first step towards establishing a structural Eurocode for the design of fibre-polymer composite structures, i.e. (Ascione, 2016), the following main clauses or sub-clauses were subject to major revisions or were added to the TS: (i) Basis of design (regarding partial factors for materials, conversion factors and creep coefficients); (ii) Ultimate limit states of sandwich structures; (iii) Creep rupture; (iv) Fatigue; (v) Adhesive joints and connections; (vi) Detailing; (vii) Structural fire design.

Unfortunately, it was not possible to introduce execution rules in the TS as they fall outside the scope of CEN/TC 250. In special cases, CEN/TC 250 may propose to develop implementation rules if no other Technical Committee will undertake the work. The process can be initiated, as desirable, with input from a substantial number of stakeholders, including contractors. CEN TC 250 followed this path, which led to entrusting WG 4 to start the drafting of provisions relating to the execution of fibre-polymer composite structures. This effort was very recently started.

The TS has been complemented by a Background Document and a collection of Worked Examples relating to the topics of the TS. The first document provides background reports for the paragraphs and justifications for the decisions that were made, and the values that were selected. The second document provides support to the designers community.

Both the documents will contribute to spreading the use of the TS within the CEN countries and elsewhere, with substantial positive impacts of an economic nature, since the existence of a body of shared rules ensures a uniform level of quality and safety in the production as well as the use of composite structures.

REFERENCES

CEN/TC 250 (2020), *Structural Eurocodes N 1250*.

Ascione, L, et al. (2016), *Prospect for New Guidance in the Design of FRP*. EUR 27666, DOI: 10.2788/22306 (online).

Keller, T. et al. (2020), *CEN Technical Specification of Fibre-Polymer Composite Structures*. SAMPE Europe Conference 2020, Amsterdam-Netherlands.

Ascione, L. et al. (2022), *Design of Fibre-Composite Structures – European Technical Specification: Overview and Scope*. Proceedings of the 20th European Conference on Composite Materials, ECCM20. 26-30 June, vol. 5, DOI: http://dx.doi.org/10.5075/epfl-298799_978-2-9701614-0-0, Lausanne, Switzerland.

CEN/TC 250 (2018), *prEN 1990: 2018 - Basis of structural and geotechnical design*.

CEN, ISO (2014), *2394: 2014 - General principles on reliability for structures*.

CEN/TC 250 (1991), *EN 1991-2: 2003, Actions on structures - Part 2: Traffic loads on bridges*.

Clarke, J.L. (1996), *Structural Design of Polymer Composites: Eurocomp Design Code and Handbook*. London: E & FN Spon.